

ASTOLOGICAL AND STARS PROVERBS

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Abstract:

The astronomical positions of the planets used in astrology to forecast the future of the native by the astrologer, for the betterment of the native. So, it is a useful science which is called as the place of light or the knowledge of light. Astronomers base their studies on research and observation. Astrology on the otherhand is the beliefs that the positioning of the stars and planets affect the way of events occur on earth."Fools obey planets while wise men Control them." Some persons have intrest to learn astrology. When they learn to some extent, they start predicting the future of the native. Beauty - Sky - Stars.The Doctor Test through your hand and the astrologer predict through the leg (Paatha)

Key Words: Signs and the Proverbs - Proverbs of the Stars - Explanation - Proverbs of Planet - Proverb Ththiyogam - Conclusion.

Introduction:

Astrology is one of the ancient Sastras of the world. It is only the oldest one among the sciences. It is not the subjects like Mathematics, Physics and chemistry which require only common sense and simple Logical think to understand these subjects easily. But astrology is an occult science and imperceptible. It requires inducement. When Ayurveda is a upa Vedha, Astrology becomes the eyes of the Vedha. The ancient saints considered the knowledge of astrology is a very important branch of the Vedha tree. And it is the root to predict the future of the individual. Astrology is the science that explains the influence of the planets and it is a divine subject of stars and luck shown by them to the life of an individual.

The great people of the western countries like Johannes Kepler, Bekkan, Pythagoras and other eminent astrologer's are the pioneers of astrology. Mr. Dante expresses that "the highest, the noblest and with out any defect". So "Astrology is consummate and an excellent phenomena". Astrologers from Babylon were called Kasdim / Kasdin (Chaldeans) in the Book of Daniel. In rabbinic literature, the term Chaldeans later was often used as a synonym with those who practiced astrology. In pre-modern Hebrew, astrology was known as hokmat ha-mazlot, "the science of the constellations". Newton had intrest in mathematics and astronomical researches.

By knowing the adverse effects of their future life, how can they avoid the unfavourable thinks happen? This type of independent thinking and improved knowledge will help them to overcome the negative or malefic effects in their life. The belief in Astrological science helps the mankind in their moral and financial progress and it is considered as more than that of the real science. There is a system of medical astrology which helps the mankind to keep their health in a good condition. There are many people who don't have belief in the actions of the planets. Still there are thousands of people say that astrology is superstition. They laugh at it, blame it and have no patience. But they will not have guts to neglect the advice of an astrologer.

Plenty of Stars

Is it possible for us to count the sand in the river and the stars on the sky?

Constituents of Myth.

We can't count the wives of Arjuna and the stars in the sky.

Darkness - Aphotic

A small star lightning vividly in the darkness (Finnish proverb)

Night

Signs and Proverbs: There are many proverbs related to astrology. Now, we will see the proverbs concerning to Signs.

Aries - Don't clash with sheep. That is - don't calsh with the person born in Aries sign.

Taurus - Don't fight with the Bull. That is - don't fight with the person born in Taurus sign.

Gemini - words of the twins is upto the grave yard or crematorium. The words of the people born in Gemini sign will not be true and come only upto the grave yard.

Cancer - Don't give space to Cancerine. If you give place to the people born in cancer will wrest the place.

Leo - Don't get anger with lion. Don't get angry with the people born in the sign Leo.

Virgo - Don't leave your son born in Virgo. Don't abandon the person born in Virgo sign.

Libra - The native of Libra will never leave the gain. The person born in Libra sign will never give off his share and dividend.

Scorpio - The person born in Scorpio will give his shoulder to help or will give his full support. The Scorpions will always help their friends.

Sagittarius - The bow man is a wise man. The person born in sagittarius is an able man, who will bow only by listening good words.

Capricorn - Capricorn people will lead a city. The person born in Capricorn will rule a kingdom.

Aquarius person will solve the problems of others.

Pisces - The person born in Pisces will be a great man of good character.

We should know some proverbs related to astrology and Planets

Moon:

Thousand stars added together, will not become the Moon

If even thousand stars combined together will not be equal to the Moon. The decision taken by thousand fools may not be equal to the decision of a single intelligent person. That becomes true by the bright Moon.

Jupiter in 3rd house - When the transit of Jupiter was in 3rd house, all the warriors of Dhuryothana's army died as 'war Heros'. So, this kind of action should be avoided when Jupiter is in 3rd house while on transit. When the Jupiter was in Janma Rasi during transit Lord Rama with his wife Sita, happened to go to forest for 14 years. When the Jupiter in Janama Rasi, he gives all troubles to the native like separation, trouble in the family, getting success in the foreign land.

If Jupiter aspects there will be crores of benefit to the native: The placement of Jupiter spoils that house where it sits. The house which gets the aspect of Jupiter definitely flourish. Jupiter represents Gold. Jupiter takes 12 years to come around the zodiac. But, Mercury comes around the Sun 4 times a year. Because, Mercury is very near to the Sun and Jupiter is far off from the Sun and so it is very easy to see Jupiter.

- **No one has lived a better life for thirty years and none has lived a worst life for thirty years.** We can see Jupiter, but not Mercury. Before the invention of telescope, an astronomer was worried that 'he is going to die' without seeing the planet Mercury.
- **The things couldn't do by the day, will be done by the Planets** and if it was not done by the Planets, it will be done by our family God successfully. Family God has the power to do all things that you wish. Family God looks after us like our parents. In some cases people go to other countries in search of their lively hood, stay there for more years and forget about their family God and their children never come to know about the whereabouts of their family God. As such they are unable to worship the same.
- **The man, who wastes his sperm, will suffer a lot.** The karaka for sperm is Venus for men and when he becomes debilitated the production of sperm is less and there starts the problem. So, when Venus gets debilitated in the 6th house of kala Purush and the native becomes sick.

"Young (Kutty) Venus will spoil the family"

The main period of Venus is not considered as good at the younger age. The natives born in the constellations of Barani - Poorvapalguni - Poorvashada the 1st dasa will start with Venus dasa. Next comes the main period of Ketu. The native born in the constellations of Aswini - Magha - Moola the Venus dasa becomes stars of Sampath Thara or Dhana Thara. In astrology Gulika is called as Kutty (small). Ravan wanted all planets in the horoscope of his son Indrajit in a strong manner. So, he ordered all planets to be in their strong and best places in Indrajit's horoscope. Listening to his order, Saturn sat in his exalted sign, Libra. Devendra thought that, if Indrajit becomes immortal, there will be more problems to Devas. So, Devendra asked Saturn to change his place in the horoscope. But, Saturn was afraid of Ravana and tried to have some other idea. Once, Goddess Parvathi to make Lord Vinayak as her guard collected all her sweating dirt and made him as his son. The same way, Saturn tried and made Gulika from his sweating dirt and made him to sit in the sign Scorpio. Scorpio is the Ayul Bhava of (8th house, house of longevity) Kala purush. Thus, Saturn made affliction to the longevity of Indrajit. Till today in Kerala, astrologers are using Gulika / Mandhi for the calculations of Ayurdhaya and for analyzing the chart for proper remedies.

If Gulika combine with kalthira karaka Venus in a male chart, he will have lots of sufferings due to his wife. If an exalted lord aspect some other exalted lord then there will be no way to beg in the native's life. But if debilitated lord aspect some other debilitated lord, then the native is lucky enough to get Raja Yoga. These rules may not work out every where. The planets are divided into two teams. One of which belong to the team of "grace", headed by Deva Guru - Jupiter and the other team of "affluence", headed by the foes to the Gods - Asura Guru Venus. No.1 team consists of 4 planets - The Sun, The moon, Mars and Jupiter. No.2. team consists of the 3 planets - Venus, Mercury, and Saturn. In the Jupiter team, only Mars and Jupiter will have the chance of becoming debilitated and aspect each other. In the Venus team there is no planet to get debilitated and look upon each other. In the same team if 2 planets at the same time get debilitated and aspect each other and in their main / sub periods they confer Raja Yoga. This rule is applicable only to the planets Mars and Jupiter in the (Deva Guru team) Grace Team. There is no chance for the other team to have this debilitated position. Especially for Mercury and Venus there is no chance for them to be opposite (7/7) position as they always move together in the Zodiac.

At this stage, the two planets of opposite teams and big enemies the Sun and Saturn have this chance of aspecting each other and at their main / sub periods they don't confer good results, if there is no connection with benefic Planets. This will affect the karakathuvras of both these planets. So, here the aspect of 2 debilitated planets, wouldn't work out. In this dasa, and in an auspicious sub - period with respect to the ascendant, the native will have an appearance of anger by one's look or words. Some times they become a hoodman.

Saturn:

- It is said that on every Saturdays we should have oil bath. On Monday to Friday we give more work to our Brain. To get it cool all men should have oil bath with gingely oil. That is good for our health.
- It is better to give money to oil vendor instead of paying fee to Doctor by taking oil bath.
- Saturn is the lord of Ayurdhaya. A man who dies on Saturday will take away one more body from this world along with it.
- When Saturn confers things, no one can stop him from giving it.
- When Saturn in the 8th house in transit, will not allow the native to wear even his inner wear. The native will have that much suffering during this period when transit Saturn is in Ashtamabava.
- The native will be trapped during the transit of Saturn in the 8th house.
- Saturn gives trouble, as such when the native suffers from cold.
- Saturn in the Janma Rasi duringtransit the native will meet with humiliation, equivalent to nose cut.
- Saturn in the 5th house during transit will make the native to fly like a cotton piece.
- Saturn in the 6th house during tansit the native will be crowned.
- Saturn in the 2th house during tansit the native will have two family lives.
- The troubles given by Saturn is equivalent to the troubles while he was in Janma Rasi.
- Saturn is reffered as sadness and obstructions.
- The aspect of Saturn makes the temple tower to a hut and makes a hut to a temple tower.
- The aspect of Saturn makes a small house to a multi-storied building and vice-versa.
- Saturn hora is considered as the best hora, for paying back the out-standing loans
- You cannot get a good day like Wednesday. It is considered as more than a golden day. The Sun and Mercury are always traveling together in the zodiac. Both travel in a distance of 28° and there is no dosha of combustion for Mercury. When both combine together forms Budha-Adhithya Yoga.
- There is no one gives like Rahu (Dragon's head).Dragon's head is a shadowish planet and it is considered as very strong one. If Rahu is in a good position in a horoscope, confers more gold and wealth. At the same time if it is in a bad position then it never hesitate to make the native to stand at the end of the street. When you delineate some wealthiest persons horoscope, you will find that in the main period of Rahu, he must have reached to the top level of his life.
- Though the king of the planetary kingdom is the Sun, Rahu becomes powerful and superior to the Sun due to, solar eclipse.

There are some more proverbs concerning 27 stars from Aswini to Revathi. Below is the information about them.

The stars and the truth

To know the myth and the astrological informations, by using stars, they formed astrological proverbs.

By misunderstanding the meaning of these proverbs they start worrying by comparing with their stars.

Stars will never make noise.

We can't count the stars on the sky and we can't straighten the dogs tail.

The beauty of sky is the stars. The beauty of woman is her hair.

One, that doesn't twinkle in the day time, twinkles in the night.

Stars never give sound. (Irish Proverb)

The constellations rule the world and the constellations are ruled / controlled by the God.

Day and Star

Auspicious time should be selected for success in any function.

Constellation / Galaxy

The poem of the sky is the constellation and the poem of the earth is women.

The stars that confer Raja Yoga-

The persons born in the constellations of Arudra, Barani, Swathi, Hasta, and Uthrashada will enjoy the Raja Yogas.

Born to rukeAswini -SkyrulerKarthika

In this above two stars if there occurs a thunder, there wouldn't be rain for 6 Karthikas.

Rules the world Bharani -

The native born in Bharani star will rule the world.The man born in Barani star will rule the World. 'Baranam'- means wearing of crown. So the day when a man wears a crown from that day he becomes the king and that is the actual meaning of that word.

The Furnace Made in Bharani Star Will Not Be Decayed: The furnace made in Bharani star will not be ruined. (The furnace put in the Saturn corner of the house in the star of Bharani will take the family to a high level). The Barani star is in the sign Aries, where the Sun is exalted. So, Barani people are considered as the ruler of the world.

It Will Rain Through Out the World, If It Rains in the Bharani Star: Life without sorrow Rohini

It is not good for the maternal uncle of the child if the child is born in Rohini star: Though people believe this statement, this is not true. Lord Krishna was born in the star Rohini and his maternal uncle Hamsa died. That is why people believe this proverb. In a horoscope, if the planet Mercury and the 5th house are weak then only this statement will be correct. Truly speaking, the people born in Rohini star will have a crowd around them and will be liked by all.

Gods favorite Arudra -

The pudding (kali) prepared on Arudra day will not be available on all the days.

Arudra is with pepper powder.

The Arudra born native will be a fraudulent

Arudra star is like a bell to be prayed and bowed by the people of the world. Lord Shiva born in Arudra star, so, it was said that without any doubt Lord Shiva should be worshipped.

The person born in Arudra will not talk much. The article gone by theft will come back to your home. It is not better to have a friend born in Arudra.

Poosam -

There is a saying that during the constellation of Pushya, even a cat will not eat old food. On that day we should do only fasting or other voluntary religious observance.

All - win Aslesha -

In the heading "Mamiyar, Marumkal" (Mother-in-law & daughter-in-law) it is said that if a girl born in Aslesha - the mother-in-law of that girl will sit in a corner. That is widow-hood.

Also mentions the same proverb.

Whatever words, Aslesha girl say will come true, like her mother-in-law. If at all the mother-in-law is sick, when Aslesha girl enters their house after marriage, the mother-in-law will be healthy. Kannan battacharya says that "the person born in Aslesha will succeed in all ventures.

Ruler of the world Makha -

There is no one in the world like makha born.

Girl in Makha star will match to Purvapalguni Boy

Father will not see the face of Makha born.

It is not good to see the Makha born girl.

You can't control the girl born in Makha.

When you forget to give the thithi to your ancestors you can give it on Makha star day. When you forget the Thithi, give it on Makha star day. The Makha star is in Leo and the Sun is the lord of that sign. So, Makha people are considered as the ruler of the universe and it is having the shape of crown.

Meaningful PurvaPalguni -

PurvaPalguni = troublesome spouse. UthraPalguni -

The boy born in UthraPalguni will have land in the village boundary.

The son in Uthra Palguni will have landed property in the village boundary.

The son in Uthra Palguni, is troublesome to all relatives.

As Venus is debilitated in Virgo, the UthraPulguni son gives more trouble.

Universal ferrying Hasta -

Child born in the star Hasta will have landed property near river.

Seeding or transplantation to be done in Hasta star.

The girl born in Hasta star will give trouble to her husband and father-in-law.

Chittra -

The father of chitta born will come down to the street.

The father of Chitta is in the street. In the Dkshinayana period the Sun gets debilitated in the "Paathalaloha" (under world) in the star of Chittra. He becomes weak. So, here the weak Sun is mentioned and Nothing else.

Swathi - in Venus there will be non stop rain.

The Swathi means, the Sun. So, the native will be an elegant man.

The best stars for conducting marriage and other functions = Swathi, Vishaka, Moola, Sravana.

The prosperity if the clan Jeyshta

Jeyshta star is not good for brother. Jeyshta is the star of "Varaha", he killed "Hiranya" the elder brother of "Irunya kasibu". So, this proverb has come to mark this occasion.

If one born in Jeyshtastar, that becomes a bad day.

If one born in Jeyshta the native will have 8 servants.

The native born in Jeyshta will construct a fort and rule the kingdom.

Jeyshta star is not good for elder brother.

Jeshta is born in a bad family

Jeyshta, baggage, Tuesday couldn't ask loan and respect Tamilnadu.

One born in the Jeyshta star will construct castle on the air.

One born in Jeyshtastar will not live a good life.

It will be better if Jeshta born girl become the eldest daughter-in-law.

Powerful one Moola -

Is Moola a deceiver or a star?

The mother-in-law of the girl born in Moola star will acquire widowhood soon.

The boy born in Moola star will rule the kingdom.

The girl born in Moola star will be the cause for the destruction of her family. (M.Sarala)

Woman born in Moola star will be a destroyer. (Pen moolamnirmoolam). It is not true. Nirmal means it is the breeze of Makasira month and it is a purified breeze and the Sun reaches the way of nirmalavaikund. The place where ever he goes, the native born in Moola star will be underdestruction.

This is not true. Moola means root, bottom portion. This is a medical proverb. A male tree root has herbal medical effect which cures and makes a man strong. But, the female tree root is not too strong, and cause destruction. That was the real truth and the above said astrological proverb is not true.

The real meaning of this proverb is "Moola comes in the Tamil month of AANI will rule the kingdom. i.e. if the native is born in the star of Moola in the month of AANI (June,July) and the Jupiter aspect the Moon and when a good dasa / bukthi arise, then he get the chance of ruling the kingdom. If born in the 4th pada of Moola, he will defeat his enemies. So, we should not support the false rule of avoiding Moola star for marriage. Nowadays we can see Moola star people leading a happy life with their family. And there is no trouble to the father -in-law or the mother in law. If in a house first born is a male child, then three female child, fourth one is male in moola and the 5th one is female will live happily. 5th male child also will live happily. 7th female child will die and the 8 child will be the cause of the destruction, and the 10th male will become a fool. Virtue will make you grow Poorvashada. Poorva ashada means, heading towards the success. So, they will fight for the success. Poorva Shada - trouble for Mangalya is wrongly understood. The real meaning is Keeping the thread in a straight line and doing the job in a correct manner.

You cannot fight with the person born in poorvashada star.

Refugee will give birth to a girl child and that too on Friday poorvashadastar. (always fighting). In Poorvashada if a girl born, it is not good. Poorvashada person always fight with others. A boy born in Poorvashada is good. The native born in this star should give birth to a child before thirty years of age. Other wise they will not have child. There is a saying that - Born in Poorvashada there is no guarantee for Mangalya thread. Here NOOL = Thread = means Book. So, we should understand that they will not take much interest in education at the young age. But afterwards their education will be good. So, this proverb is not true.

Troublers out Uthraahada -

The one born in Uthraahada will have landed property in the village border.

No scarcity for food for the native born in Uthraahada. They will have everything in their backyard.

They will guide their younger sister and brothers in a good way.

Gives rise to anything Shravana -

There is no enemy to Shravana born. They will succeed in all. They will rule the world. No one can defeat them. Their fame will ever remain.

Turns bran into gold Dhanishta -

One born in Dhanishta star will have Bran pot full of gold.

If the native born in dhanishta on the month of aavani (Aug - Sep), the proverb is applicable. In that month the sun is in simamrasi which is directly seen to kumbamrasi moon so that the day would become good and productive.

If they touch some thing with their hand, that becomes gold.

The native born in Dhanishta star should not marry others, other than relatives.

The promise of grace Sathabhisha-

They have no self knowledge and they don't listen to the words of others.

If there is no self knowledge at least they should listen to others.

A child should not take birth on these days and stars.

From the astrological old songs in Tamil

On Sunday in Bharani star.

On Monday in Chitta star.

On Tuesday in Uthraahada star.

On Wednesday in Dhanishta star.

On Thursday in Jeyshta star.

On Friday in Poorvashada star.

On Saturday in Revathi star.

If a child takes birth on these day and star, will confer lot of problems in the family.

It is not to have births of child on these days and stars and auspicious functions are not to be performed on these days.

The Proverb about this

There is another saying that, it is lucky to have death on the thithi “Ekadasi” and the cremation on “Duvadasi.” Fasting on ekadasi is very good. This day is the day when Goddess Lakshmi married to Lord Maha Vishnu. On duvadasi people end the fasting and pray Lord Vishnu. On that day they eat the food with Sesbania grandiflora (edible leaves) and Indian gooseberry. Lord Krishna was born on the day of Ashtami thithi. Lord Rama was born on the Navami thithi. We are all celebrating these days as auspicious days. But, at the same time we are not ready to celebrate some or other functions on these days. Because we think that these days are inauspicious days. Why is this confusion?

Jothda Rathina. Dr. K.P.Vidhya Dharan.

Generally these days are considered as inauspicious. But, in Navarathiri this Ashtami, navami days, Sri Rama Navami and Krishnashtami are considered as auspicious. On these days 8, 17, 26 the native can do anything, though these days fall on Ashtami. Because, these numbers match to ashtami, the 8th thithi of the fifteen (15+15 = 30 thithi's) thithi's. The same way no 8 is represented by Saturn. So, the people born in Capricorn and Aquarius signs can perform any auspicious functions. The people who have strong Saturn (as a ruler or exalted) in their Chart too can perform auspicious functions on these days. The Navami is the 9th thithi. So, 9, 18, 27 number people can perform auspicious functions on this Navami day. As Navami is ruled by Mars, the Aries and Scorpio sign natives can perform any auspicious functions. The people who have strong Mars (as a ruler or exalted) in their Chart too can perform auspicious functions on these days.

There is a saying by our ancestors that the things done in the Ashtami, Navami Thithis will not succeed. Why? This was said so, because those actions performed will prolong and will not come to an end. We may happen to continue to do those actions for a long time. Lord Krishna suffered a lot from his day of birth, as he was born on Navami thithi. As he is the Avathar of God, he could manage all his troubles.

As Lord Rama Was born on Navami, he happened to leave the throne and went to forest along with his beloved wife. Afterwards, as we all know, he met with many problems.

Even God has all these problems; we men should avoid conducting auspicious functions and actions (house warming ceremony, procuring, registering properties and any other important functions. etc.) on these days. But, on this thithis we can perform Divine activities (Deeksha, Chanting Mantraas, doing Homaas. etc) with out any hesitation. More over the following things can be done in these two thithis. To set fire in brick kiln, to file a suit on enemies, to use the arms (like gun.etc), to attack on our enemical countries.

- It is not auspicious to do things in the thithis Ashtmi and Navmi.
- We should do cremation of the body on Dhuvathasithithi, when a man dies on Ekadhasi.
- We should avoid doing things on the death thithis of our parents.
- The people die on the 1st and 2nd day of the Tamil month “thai” will reach the high abode.(heaven,Moksha).

Is the astrological proverbs are true? Let us get the answer from Dr.K.P.Vidyadharan:-

- Transit Jupiter in 10th create problems in the Job/Profession
- If the snakes are present in the 10th, money would flourish.
- The day and planet never do anything to poor people.
- The man caught by the Saturn will not be able to buy even a ragged cloth from the market.
- When Mars placed in the Virgo sign, even the sea will become dry land.
- In this sign you will have the luck to lead a kingdom, but in Amsa you will have the luck to herd asses.
- Jupiter's aspect confers crores of benefits.
- Aquarians will pour with silver pot.
- Makha girl with Poorvapulguni boy is made for each other.
- You may get even Gold, but, you may not get a good day as Wednesday/ Mercury.
- Rahu in Aries confer superiority.
- Ketu in Libra will solve all problems.
- The native born in chitta (chaitra) month will wander in the street.
- Venus in Swati star will give incessant rain.
- Hidden Mercury confers excellent education.
- Child born in the month of chaitra confers deterioration.
- The father of the child born in the month of chaitra will wander in the streets.
- If Jupiter in the 10th house, the native will lose his job.
- The Moon will follow the route of fate.
- One born in Dhanishta star will have Bran pot full of gold.

- If Jupiter gives, Saturn will obstruct. But, if Saturn gives no one could stop it.
- The house where Saturn aspect to, will be destroyed.
- We should have Oil bath on Saturdays.
- The place where there is impurity, Goddess will not stay there.
- For the native who ran away from home, you will find Jupiter in the 9th house in his chart.
- You need not go to good function (where gram food prepared), but you should not avoid going to death (where we use fire) function.
- If Saturn in 8th house, the native will be long lived. (Poorna Ayu).
- There is none other than; Saturn either will give destruction to the native or something superior to him.
- It is trouble some for the native, if Saturn is positioned in the 8th house.
- The place where Jupiter stay will be affected / destroyed.
- The place where Saturn aspect will be affected.
- You can do something in the night, but not in Rahu kal.
- Barani born will rule the country / world.
- Makha gril will rule the universe.
- Jeyshta born will construct a fort and rule.
- Moola in the month of (Tamil month) AANI will rule the kingdom and Moola in the month of Virgo (Tamil month Purattasi) will spoil the family.

Conclusion:

There are some people have belief in astrology, some have no faith in this subject. But, these astrological proverbs have reached both this category of people. Astrology is derived from stars, signs and logically explained from vedhas. It is said to be the eyes of vedhas. Some say astrology is called as the “messages from the stars”. No intelligent brain can deny, how the total influence of the planets affect the native, his body condition, mind's ability, myth, religious thoughts and desires etc. Astrology we should not get confused with death, devilry and palmistry. It is the configuration of our past karma and the prediction of the future is designed by our birth chart with the current planets position at the time of our birth.

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